

ANALYSIS OF THE POPULATION STRUCTURE OF PHYTOPHTHORA NICOTIANAE USING MICROSATELLITE MARKERS. A. Biasi¹, F.N. Martin², S.O. Cacciola³, N.J. Grünwald⁴, M. Evoli³, L. Schena¹. ¹Dipartimento di Agraria, Università degli Studi Mediterranea, Località Feo di Vito, 89124 Reggio Calabria, Italy. ²United States Department of Agriculture- Agricultural Research Service, 1636 East Alisal Street, Salinas, CA 93905. ³Dipartimento di Gestione dei Sistemi Agroalimentari e Ambientali, Università degli Studi, Via Santa Sofia, 100, 95123 Catania, Italy. ⁴Horticultural Crops Research Laboratory, US Department of Agriculture Agricultural Research Service, Corvallis, OR 97330. E-mail: lschena@unirc.it

A panel of single sequence repeats (SSRs) was screened taking advantage of the recently sequenced genomes of *Phytophthora nicotianae* from 6 different isolates and selected markers were accurately evaluated using *in silico* and experimental approaches. The best 9 performing SSRs were used to characterize a wide population of *P. nicotianae* (268 isolates) from a broad range of hosts and geographic localities. Primers were optimized to be used in a duplex approach with two differently labeled fluorescent dyes, in order to reduce costs and time of the analyses. A total of 129 different multilocus genotypes (MLG) were identified, with a different rate of polymorphism within the markers used. Analyses revealed a prevalence of clonality in productive orchards, while sexual recombination seemed to be more widespread in nurseries. A strong association between genetic groups and host was revealed for most *Citrus* isolates, while a significant geographical structuring was recovered for isolates from tobacco (sourced in Australia and United States) and from pummelo (*Citrus maxima*) sourced in Vietnam. For other *Citrus* species a typical panmictic distribution was revealed. Differences in the population structure were likely to be influenced by propagation and cultivation systems. Isolates from potted ornamental and citrus (excepted pummelo) are probably diffused worldwide with infected plant materials. In contrast tobacco is propagated by seeds which do not contribute to the spread of the pathogen. As regards to *C. maxima*, this species is a native plant of Vietnam and plant materials were not introduced from other countries suggesting a specific co-evolution with *P. nicotianae*.

VIRUS AND VIROID COMMUNITY DETECTION BY METAGENOMIC ANALYSIS. G. Licciardello¹, R. Ferraro¹, M. Russo¹, S. M. Dai², Z.N. Deng², A. Catara¹. ¹Parco Scientifico e Tecnologico della Sicilia, z.i. Stradale Lancia 57, 95121 Catania, Italy. ²National Center for Citrus Improvement (Changsha), Hunan Agricultural University, Hunan 410128, P.R. China. E-mail: glicciardello@pstsicilia.it

A source plant inducing symptoms of tristeza seedling yellows in sour orange, yellow vein clearing in lemon and mottled and tattered leaves in Carrizo citrange was analysed by deep sequencing of sRNA (18-26 nt) using Illumina technology. The abundance of virus- and viroid-derived siRNAs was estimated by aligning the filtered reads on the genomes of 17 *Citrus tristeza virus* (CTV) isolates, 24 viroids, one *Citrus yellow vein clearing virus* (CYVCV) genome and one *Citrus tatter leaf virus* (CTLV) genome. The analysis showed a prevalent reads abundance of 17,604,200 with CTV isolates belonging to the VT genotype. A typical structural organization with 12 open reading frames (ORFs) and two untranslated regions (UTRs) was identified in the resulting consensus sequence, approximately 19.3 kb in length. When the sRNA library was aligned against the CYVCV isolate Y1, a total of 159,585 reads were able to reconstruct the full genome with an overall nucleotide identity of 98%. Computational analysis of the RNA genome

sequence, 7529 nt in length, predicted six ORFs and two UTRs. The complete genome sequence of CTLV, constituted by two ORFs and a poly (A) tail at the 3' end, was also reconstructed. The alignment with viroid genomes showed the presence of CDVd, HSVd, CVdII, CVdIII and CVdIV with an abundance of about 30,000-40,000 reads. The study demonstrated that deep sequencing and bioinformatic analyses can identify a viral community in a host in agreement with indexing results, although in some cases bioindexing and PCR detection are necessary to confirm the results.

BEEET NECROTIC YELLOW VEIN VIRUS AND BEEET SOIL-BORNE MOSAIC VIRUS: A PRELIMINARY STUDY OF RNAs REASSORTMENT. M. Dall'Ara¹, A. Delbianco¹, S. Bouzoubaa², E. Klein², D. Gilmer², C. Ratti¹. ¹DipSA - Plant Pathology, University of Bologna, Viale G. Fanin, 40 - 40127 Bologna, Italy. ²Institut de Biologie Moléculaire des Plantes du CNRS, Université de Strasbourg, 12 rue du Général Zimmer, 67084 Strasbourg Cedex, France. E-mail: david.gilmer@ibmp-cnrs.unistra.fr

Beet necrotic yellow vein virus (BNYVV) and *Beet soil-borne mosaic virus* (BSBMV) (*Benyviridae* family) are distinct but closely related species possessing the same host range, vector and multipartite genome of four to five ssRNAs (+) that represent an interesting model to study plant-virus interactions.

RNA-1 and -2 combination (helper strain) is essential for the infection and the replication of both viruses, while RNA-3 and -4 are accessory RNAs playing important roles in plant-virus and virus-vector interactions, respectively.

Previous work demonstrated on the one hand the ability of BNYVV/BSBMV helper strains to handle the replication and packaging of cognate small RNA segments, on the other hand, the availability of a functional exchange of genomic RNA-1 between both viral species. Interestingly, one of the two chimeric combinations induced a strong necrosis of the infected *Chenopodium quinoa* leading to a dead end for the recombinant virus. Such dramatic cell death or incompatible reaction could explain why no natural chimeras have ever been found in plant naturally infected with both viruses.

As both viruses could co-exist in the same plant, a mixture of both genomic RNAs in the same cell should be avoided, particularly when the virus moves at a long distance.

The unavailability of benyviridae genomic RNA reassortment, in particular for RNA-1, has been tested in *C. quinoa* and *Nicotiana benthamiana* local and systemic host, respectively, using BNYVV/BSBMV full-length infectious cDNA clones and agroclones in a genetic reverse approach.

SEQUENCING AN UNCONVENTIONAL VIRUS GENOME: THE MULBERRY BADNAVIRUS-1 CASE. M. Chiumenti¹, M. Morelli¹, T. Elbeaino², L. Stavolone³, A. De Stradis³, A. Minafra³, G.P. Martelli¹. ¹Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti, Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²Istituto Agronomico Mediterraneo di Bari (IAMB), 70010 Valenzano (Bari), Italy. ³Istituto di Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante (CNR-IPSP), UOS Bari, 70126 Bari, Italy. E-mail: michela.chiumenti@gmail.com

Mulberry is a deciduous tree belonging to the *Moraceae* family. Although its economical importance and spreading all over the world, due mainly to the domesticated silkworm (*Bombyx mori* L.) breeding, to date, only few information are available about viral and virus-like diseases affecting this plant.

In 2012 a small fragment of a *Badnavirus* DNA genome was sequenced after a DOP-PCR assay conducted on a mulberry plant,

originated from Lebanon, showing symptoms of leaf mottling and vein yellowing. The virus, whose particles were observed with electron microscopy from a partially purified preparation and in tissue thin sections, was provisionally named Mulberry badnavirus-1 (MBV-1). Since different attempts of completing the full-length genome sequence through a conventional approach failed, a small RNA library was constructed for deep sequencing and run according to Illumina protocol.

sRNAs analysis allowed the design of a set of primers used in PCR for the achievement of the full length sequence. The complete genome contains all the sequence features and the characteristic functional domains of the genus *Badnavirus* (highest nucleotide similarity shared with FBV-1 at 54%). By contrast to the badnaviruses, with genomes encoding for 3-4 ORFs, MBV-1 resembles genome organization of *Petunia vein clearing virus* (PVCV), which bears a single ORF.

The study of the distribution of sRNA on the MBV-1 complete genome showed a tidy prevalence of 21- and 22-nt reads, differently from other viruses in the *Caulimoviridae* family, featuring a nuclear replication and typically supporting an accumulation of the 24-nt sRNAs involved in methylation processes.

EVIDENCES OF THE EXISTENCE OF GRAPEVINE PINOT GRIS VIRUS ISOLATES SHOWING DIVERSE PATHOGENICITY. M. Morelli¹, A. Giampetruzzi¹, P. Bianchedi², P. Saldarelli¹, V. Gualandri². ¹Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante del C.N.R. UOS Bari, Via Amendola, 165/A, 70126 Bari, Italy. ²FEM-IASMA, Centre for Technology Transfer, via E. Mach, 1 38010, San Michele all'Adige (TN) Italy E-mail: p.saldarelli@ba.iov.cnr.it

Grapevine Pinot gris virus (GPGV) is a recently described trichovirus, discovered by next generation sequencing (NGS) in the cv Pinot gris, seemingly associated to a new grapevine disease. To define the aetiology of the disease, the virome of two additional Pinot gris accessions, showing or not symptoms, were analysed by NGS. Virus content consistently reproduced the already known virome with GPGV, *Grapevine rupestris stem pitting virus* (GRSPaV), *Grapevine Rupestris vein feathering virus* (GRVfV) and the two viroids *Hop stunt viroid* (HSVd) and *Grapevine yellow speckle viroid 1* (GYSVd-1), infecting either the symptomatic or the symptomless plants. Whole genome phylogenetic analysis on seven GPGV isolates, including three isolates originating from Czech Republic and Slovak Republic and consensus sequences assembled by NGS, clearly clustered those infecting symptomatic vines. We therefore extended the analysis to two genomic regions, comprising the RNA polymerase RNA dependent domain of the replicase gene and part of the movement protein, on a group of accessions from Trentino, free from relevant viruses involved in leafroll, infectious degenerations and rugose-wood associated grapevine diseases. Maximum likelihood and Bayesian phylogenetic analyses of nucleotide sequences, proved that isolates from vines with symptoms form a clade distinct from those of symptomless vines, thus confirming studies on the whole genome. These results showed that GPGV virus populations from Trentino underwent, in the infected vines, a different evolutionary dynamic, not related with the vine variety, which selected for isolates with different pathogenicity.

VALIDATION OF A RAPID AND SENSITIVE DIAGNOSTIC PROTOCOL FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF PLUM POX VIRUS: LAMP RT-PCR. G. Pasquini¹, L. Ferretti¹, S. Lopriore², G. Airoldi², M. Barba¹. ¹Consiglio per la Ricerca e la sperimentazione in Agricoltura – Centro di Ricerca per la Patologia Vegetale

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The development of innovative rapid and reliable detection methods ‘ready to use’ directly in open field or at the borders, is an important aspect for the phytosanitary control of quarantine pathogens as *Plum pox virus* (PPV), a virus negatively impacting on stone fruits cultivation.

The use of the rapid and sensitive loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology with a portable device allows to perform the analysis directly in the field, combining the sensitivity of the technique with a practical use for a rapid interception of pathogens.

A commercial kit for the diagnosis of PPV based on LAMP technology (Bioteltec) has been validated by the calculation of the performance criteria (ISO 17025) compared with those obtained for a real time RT-PCR in a national Italian ringtest. All experiments were performed with a Bioteltec commercial kit and the Genie® II Instrument (Optigene Ltd.), starting from total RNAs (TRNA) extracted from target and no-target reference samples by a simple and rapid extraction kit (Bioteltec) and by RNeasy Plant minikit (Qiagen).

LAMP RT-PCR resulted to be a very efficient and rapid technology for PPV detection, showing a higher analytical sensitivity than RT-PCR, both with sensitive or rapid TRNA extraction methods, with a comparable diagnostic accuracy and repeatability, resulting very useful for the diagnosis of the virus, also directly in the field.

DRAFT GENOMES OF AN ITALIAN STRAIN OF PSEUDOMONAS SAVASTANOI PV. SAVASTANOI AND OF TWO ENDOPHYTES LIVING IN THE OLIVE KNOTS. C. Moretti¹, C. Cortese¹, D. Passos da Silva², G. DeVescovi², E. Torelli³, C. Ramos⁴, V. Venturi², G. Firrao³, R. Buonauro¹. ¹Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Ambientali, Università di Perugia, Via Borgo XX Giugno 74 – 06121- Perugia, Italy. ²Centre for Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, Trieste, Italy. ³Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie e Ambientali, Università degli Studi di Udine, Udine, Italy. ⁴Área de Genética, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Málaga, Instituto de Hortofruticultura Subtropical y Mediterránea “La Mayora” (IHSM-UMA-CSIC), Málaga, Spain. E-mail: chiara.moretti@unipg.it

Knots caused by *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* in olive trees provide an interesting niche for studying bacterial multispecies interactions. Among the high number of bacterial endophytes detected inside the olive knots by metagenomics, those belonging to the genera *Pantoea*, *Pectobacterium*, *Erwinia* and *Curtobacterium* are the most represented. Our attention is focused on two endophytic bacterial species, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Erwinia oleae*, which cause an increase in disease severity when co-inoculated with *P. savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* in olive plants. To better understand the molecular basis of the interaction between the pathogen and the endophytes, we sequenced their genomes. The comparison of the *P. savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* genome with that of the previously sequenced strain NCPPB 3335 provides useful information to explain the different extend of virulence the two strains show. In the *E. oleae* genome, the quorum sensing system is present and knockout mutants of *luxI/R* genes homologs were obtained. We are verifying whether *E. oleae* undergoes inter-species communication with *P. savastanoi* pv. *savastanoi* through this system. *In silico* analysis of *P. agglomerans* genome reveals the presence of a complete *hrp/hrc* gene cluster, which explains the capability of this strain to induce hypersensitive reaction in tobacco plants. This cluster shows remarkable synteny and high sequence similarity with *Erwinia amylovora* and *Erwinia pyrifoliae* homologs. Mutants of *hrpN*, *hrpY* and *hrpJ* genes were obtained and their phenotypes will be described.